

Supporting Information

Π - Π Stacking Complex Induces Three-Component Coupling Reactions To Synthesize Functionalized Amines

*T. Zhang, J. Vanderghinste, A. Guidetti, S. V. Doorslaer, G. Barcaro, S. Monti, S. Das**

1.1 Chemicals and solvents

All reagents and solvents were purchased from certified chemical vendors and used without prior purification. Demineralized water was obtained through deionization of tap water using a EUROTEC L4 reverse osmosis installation. This instrument filters out salts by means of a semi-permeable membrane. Water that was used never exceeded a conductivity of 0.5 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. Gases were purchased in high-pressured cylinders (200 bar) and converted to the desired pressure by means of a pressure regulator.

1.2 Analysis

1.2.1 Nuclear magnetic resonance

^1H NMR (400 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz) spectra were recorded using a Bruker Avance III Fourier Transform NMR spectrometer at 300 K unless explicitly stated otherwise, using deuterated solvents as internal standard (^1H : δ 7.26 ppm and ^{13}C $\{^1\text{H}\}$: δ 77.2 ppm in CDCl_3 ; ^1H : δ 2.50 ppm and ^{13}C $\{^1\text{H}\}$: δ 39.52 in DMSO-d_6). Chemical shifts (δ) were expressed in ppm and coupling constants (J) in Hertz (Hz). Splitting patterns are reported as: s (singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), q (quadruplet), p (pentuplet), m (multiplet) or combinations thereof. Integration of the signals is presented as the number of hydrogen atoms.

1.2.2 Chromatography

Thin-layer chromatography was performed using a heptane/ethyl acetate (EtOAc) solvent system as mobile phase and a 0.20 mm silica gel on an aluminium plate (Machery-Nagel Precoated TLC sheets Alugram® SIL G/UV254) as stationary phase. Visualization of the 'spots' was enhanced by illumination with UV-light (254 nm).

Flash chromatography was performed using an automatic chromatographic system (Biotage® or Combiflash®) with on-line UV-detection (254 nm and 280 nm unless explicitly stated otherwise). A heptane/EtOAc solvent system was used as mobile phase and commercial silica cartridges (12-80 g, Grace®) as stationary phase.

1.3 Optimization of reaction conditions

Table S1. Optimization of three-component coupling reactions.

Entry ^a	Variations	Yield of 5a (%) ^b
1	none	72(63 ^c)
2	DCM (1 mL)	50
3	1.5 equiv. acrylate	62
4	HE (2 equiv.)	72
5	HE 4b (1.5 equiv.)	58
6	4-Ph-HE (1.5 equiv.)	n.ob.
7	4-Cyclohexane-HE (1.5 equiv.)	n.ob.
8	DMSO (1 mL)	61
9	MeCN (1 mL)	60
10	No HE	n.ob.
11	No light	n.ob.
12	Pre-formed imine	35
13	40 W 390 nm Kessil lamp	30
14	40 W 427 nm Kessil lamp	39

^aReaction conditions: amine (0.2 mmol), aldehyde (0.2 mmol), acrylate (0.4 mmol), solvent (1 mL). ^bYield was determined by ¹H NMR with 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as internal standard. ^cIsolated yields.

Table S2. Acid screening for coupling reactions with unactivated aldehydes.

Entry	additives	Yield (%) ^a
1	TFA (0.1 equiv.)	n. ob.
2	Octanic acid (0.1 equiv.)	31
3	Octanic acid (0.1 equiv.), 2 equiv. aldehyde	34
4	Acetic acid (0.1 equiv.)	45(42 ^b)
5	Butyric acid (0.1 equiv.)	n. ob.
6	Valeric acid (0.1 equiv.)	n. ob.
7	Hexanoic acid (0.1 equiv.)	trace
8	4-Methylpentanoic acid (0.1 equiv.)	n. ob.

^aYield was determined by ¹H NMR with 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as internal standard. ^bIsolated yields.

1.4 Mechanistic studies

1.4.1 Quenching experiment

Table S3. Quenching experiments.

Entry	Quencher (2 equiv.)	Yield (%) ^a
1	TEMPO	13
2	CuCl ₂	19
3	Under air	8

^aYield was determined by ¹H NMR with 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as internal standard.

1.4.2 Stern-Volmer plot

Figure S1. Fluorescence quenching experiments were carried out with Cary Eclipse Fluorescence Spectrometer. Amine: *p*-anisidine (A), aldehyde: benzaldehyde (B), imine: *N*-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylmethanimine (C) as fluorescence quenchers. Stern-Volmer plot with potential quenchers (D).

1.4.3 Labeling/control experiments and KIE analysis

1.4.4 UV-Vis absorption studies

Figure S2. UV-Vis absorption studies were performed on a Shimadzu UV-2600 spectrophotometer.

Stock solutions of *N*-benzylidene-4-methoxyaniline and Hantzsch ester were prepared in vials, respectively. From the UV-Vis spectra, the mixture of imine and Hantzsch ester showed no observable 'red shift'. We assumed that the lifetime of ionic complex is short and it is difficult to be experimentally detected via UV-Vis absorption analysis.

1.4.5 Electrochemical Measurements

The electrochemical redox potentials were obtained using a Metrohm Autolab potentiostat-galvanostat PGSTAT204 fitted with a glassy carbon (GC) working electrode (diameter = 3 mm), an Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference electrode and a Pt-foil counter electrode, attached to a PC using Nova v2.1.5 software. 0.2 mmol samples were dissolved in 20 mL 0.1 M tetra-*n*-butylammonium hexafluorophosphate in dry, degassed acetonitrile. Reductions were measured by scanning potentials in the negative direction and oxidations in the positive direction. The obtained value was referenced to Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl).

Figure S3. Cyclic voltammogram of Hantzsch ester 4a.

Figure S4. Cyclic voltammogram of *N*-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylmethanimine.

Figure S5. Cyclic voltammogram of methyl-4-(benzylideneamino)benzoate.

Figure S6. Cyclic voltammogram of N,1-diphenylmethanimine.

Figure S7. Cyclic voltammogram of 1-(4-fluorophenyl)-*N*-phenylmethanimine.

Figure S8. Cyclic voltammogram of 2,6-dimethoxy-4-(((4-methoxyphenyl)imino)methyl)phenol.

The redox potentials of Hantzsch ester and representative imines were measured. The redox potentials of imines with electron-donating groups or electron-withdrawing groups on the both amine part or aldehyde part are all located within the potential range between ca. -1.5 V to -2.0 V vs. Ag/AgCl, which are consistent with the literatures.^[1, 2] Therefore, the reported imines in the manuscript can be reduced by HE **4a** by single-electron transfer via EDA complexes.

Figure S9. Cyclic voltammogram of mixture of HE and model imine (1:1) with different scan rates.

Figure S10. Cyclic voltammogram titration of HE in model imine (10 mM).

Figure S11. Cyclic voltammogram titration of HE in model imine (10 mM).

As shown in **Figure S9**, the cyclic voltammetry of mixture of HE and model imine showed not only peaks of HE and imine but also one new peak with lower reduction potential. To further analyze the new peak, cyclic voltammetry titration of HE in imine (10 mM) has been carried out. It is clear that the current of new peak increased linearly with increasing concentration of added HE (**Figure S10**). The peak changes of imine and HE were difficult to see since the influence of peak overlap. However, when the concentration of HE **4a** reached 12 mM, the current of imine peak was clearly dropped and the concentration of new peak was further increased (**Figure S11**). Therefore, we proposed that this new peak was generated by the complex of HE and imine.

1.5 Computational Chemistry and NEB calculations

1.5.1 Computational Chemistry calculations

We investigated the effect of blue light LED on imine-Hantzsch ester complexes in different protonation states, namely neutral molecules or ionic forms, by considering that the Hantzsch esters were extensively used in hydrogen transfer reactions as an electron donor and a proton source in several photoredox processes.

First, we generated possible structures of the complex by a multiobjective genetic algorithm based on a classical force field [3] and optimized all of them (198 in all) at the B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory in a continuum solvent description rendered through the polarizable continuum model (PCM) in its integral equation formalism (IEF), [4] choosing dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, $\epsilon = 46.70$) as the dominant solvent species acting on the supermolecule. We identified two prevalent arrangements where the phenyl ring of the aldehyde and the ring of the Hantzsch ester were parallel (stacked but shifted) or almost perpendicular (T-shaped) (**Figure S12**). In the stacked ring configuration (ester and 4-methoxyphenyl rings), where both of the molecules are neutral, the distance between the ring planes is approximately 5 Å, and the Hantzsch ester NH bond points toward the methoxy oxygen of the imine molecule. The dipole moment of the complex is around 3 Debye. Instead, in the stacked ionic complex, which is made of electron-donating-accepting moieties linked by a π -system with a separation of the planes of about 4 Å (which is shorter than in the neutral molecules case), a distance between the nitrogens of 4.04 Å, and a dipole moment of about 16 Debye, the rings are shifted, and the two nitrogens are on top of each other (**Figure S12**). As done by other authors [5], we calculated the energy difference between the complex and the sum of the energy of the isolated species and found that it was approximately -8.5 kcal/mol. This validated the stability of this particular assembly. In the hydrogen-bonded complex, where the molecules are in perpendicular orientation, the nitrogen atoms' distance is about 3.11 Å, and each species is neutral because the only stable configuration is the one with the hydrogen linked to the ester. Indeed, although it was linked to the imine in the starting structure, the hydrogen of this bond migrated onto the nitrogen of the Hantzsch ester during the optimization, producing a complex with a relatively low dipole moment of about 7 Debye.

To simulate the UV-vis spectra, we chose the TD-DFT method, combined with the continuum solvent approach, because it was benchmarked on many different systems, which included compounds similar to the molecules examined in this study, and it was used by other authors such as Gaunt and co-workers in their work^[6] to reasonably reproduce the main experimental features of the absorption (CAM-B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory). Reliable reference values directly comparable with the molecular models were not available. We checked our choice by examining the experimental UV-vis spectra of the Hantzsch ester (HE) available in the supporting materials.^[7] There, the spectrum of HE in DMSO showed an absorption peak at about 370 nm (**Figure S12**). In our case, the peak of HE is at about 350 nm. This 5% discrepancy can be considered acceptable.

Figure S12. Top. Optimized geometries of the H-bonded and stacked structures (a, b). The neutral stacked and ionic complexes are superimposed for comparison (b) and shown separately (c, d - top view) to highlight the position of the N atoms. **Bottom.** CAM-B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)/DMSO absorption spectrum of the H-bonded (gray line) and stacked-rings complexes optimized at the B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p) level in DMSO.

Stacked Configuration (Figure 3) – cartesian coordinates

C	-4.33802800	-0.64660500	0.91540400
C	-3.23996500	-1.17106000	1.82422100
C	-3.55234000	-1.60485200	3.10113200
N	-4.82398100	-1.64648800	3.59490100
C	-5.86698600	-1.37084200	2.77703600
C	-5.72251100	-0.97488600	1.44768100
C	-2.51742300	-2.07875000	4.09675700
C	-7.21164000	-1.52363200	3.45230900
C	-1.87512900	-1.13525500	1.33929100
O	-1.79403200	-0.53144500	0.10834200
C	-0.48478600	-0.43909600	-0.48991300
C	-0.63056300	0.28266800	-1.81559600
C	-6.86375300	-0.71434200	0.59886800
O	-6.48216500	-0.18164500	-0.61161900
C	-7.53391900	0.12786300	-1.54904200
C	-6.89167300	0.71639100	-2.79036600
O	-0.85763500	-1.56048600	1.88670500
O	-8.05734800	-0.91234300	0.83394500
N	-5.52758700	-5.05483100	1.53671600
C	-5.56951500	-4.32609000	0.45078900
C	-4.51179700	-4.21812800	-0.51766900
C	-3.30522000	-4.94767400	-0.44189100
C	-2.35257600	-4.81563800	-1.43798100
C	-2.58210800	-3.96456600	-2.52616600
C	-3.77024700	-3.24131700	-2.61428300
C	-4.73000100	-3.36344600	-1.61714600
C	-6.58788700	-5.32286700	2.44270900
C	-6.25896000	-5.76146200	3.72463400
C	-7.25669300	-6.04133100	4.65181700
C	-8.60064100	-5.88330700	4.29191300
C	-8.92565300	-5.45783600	2.99315100
C	-7.93142900	-5.18507500	2.07195500
H	-5.21947500	-5.87457100	4.01093000
H	-6.97558300	-6.37443000	5.64069000
H	-9.96898900	-5.36234300	2.71964200
H	-8.20929900	-4.88953400	1.06839700
H	-3.10623900	-5.62558700	0.38006400
H	-5.65464500	-2.80289600	-1.68295100
H	-1.42973300	-5.37922800	-1.37664200

H	-3.94810300	-2.58402900	-3.45639700
H	-1.83300900	-3.87232400	-3.30370500
H	-6.49617700	-3.80153100	0.25633200
H	-4.23181300	0.44223800	0.77479900
H	-4.21273400	-1.05529300	-0.09177100
H	-7.78822300	-2.34421100	3.02045600
H	-7.04798700	-1.72202500	4.51177200
H	-7.82388800	-0.62733400	3.33506500
H	-3.01090300	-2.26232200	5.05152700
H	-2.03607100	-3.00085400	3.76060500
H	-1.71570900	-1.35011900	4.22988200
H	-0.08095000	-1.44593900	-0.62472200
H	0.18178200	0.10023400	0.18752700
H	0.34820700	0.37027500	-2.29478300
H	-1.29363400	-0.26371700	-2.49062200
H	-1.03193100	1.28899600	-1.67274700
H	-8.08963000	-0.78458500	-1.78074300
H	-8.22960800	0.83267900	-1.08696100
H	-7.66649200	0.96673700	-3.51995000
H	-6.33965000	1.62892200	-2.55232300
H	-6.20397700	0.00484400	-3.25386300
O	-9.64911000	-6.12691700	5.11302200
C	-9.39295100	-6.57546800	6.45000500
H	-8.81911300	-5.83149400	7.00838800
H	-10.37088300	-6.70182800	6.90854800
H	-8.86269800	-7.53127100	6.44641900
H	-4.64637000	-5.49990400	1.77471400

HB-bonded Configuration (Figure 3) – cartesian coordinates

C	-3.49433800	0.05398100	0.46374700
C	-3.28449800	-0.30129400	1.80457400
C	-3.89382400	-1.42557900	2.34145400
C	-4.70906800	-2.24135500	1.54493000
C	-4.90686300	-1.90919200	0.20315700
C	-4.29976200	-0.76705900	-0.32699900
H	-2.65001400	0.31856900	2.42761200
H	-3.74342900	-1.69114100	3.38142700
H	-5.52086200	-2.52261800	-0.44204600
H	-4.45108300	-0.52646600	-1.37301500
O	-5.25370000	-3.33059500	2.16538800
C	-6.08836700	-4.20244400	1.40051600
H	-6.40788100	-4.98458200	2.08629500
H	-6.96581200	-3.67396500	1.01644900
H	-5.53569200	-4.65012200	0.56923200
N	-2.79833600	1.16518500	-0.08270900
C	-2.58729300	3.32337700	-1.06546000
C	-1.54676200	2.98280400	-1.94195100
C	-2.83810200	4.68121100	-0.81374400
C	-0.76986200	3.96980300	-2.54264900
H	-1.36343600	1.93919600	-2.16504100
C	-2.04940100	5.66727500	-1.40168600
H	-3.63224100	4.97591200	-0.13909200
C	-1.01589200	5.31537700	-2.26988900
H	0.02219800	3.68916200	-3.22753100
H	-2.24249700	6.71095300	-1.18161300
H	-0.41076300	6.08507400	-2.73504000
C	0.58037100	-0.76821600	-0.90584800
C	1.01139400	0.88004800	0.84466300
C	1.85642900	-1.24139100	-0.84364400
C	2.30368500	0.46394400	0.98233000
N	0.18319600	0.25679600	-0.06923000
H	-0.77894200	0.60682000	-0.15920300
C	2.86606700	-0.67233400	0.14043400
H	3.23863900	-1.47058400	0.79238500
H	3.75298700	-0.32390400	-0.39990000
C	0.34316300	1.99044900	1.61018300

H	0.87537800	2.93199600	1.47071800
H	-0.68839800	2.11033100	1.27858400
H	0.35070000	1.78493000	2.68141500
C	-0.50857800	-1.24161100	-1.82979800
H	-1.44215600	-0.75375000	-1.55384600
H	-0.27004000	-1.00281700	-2.86780500
H	-0.63654300	-2.32165300	-1.77219300
C	2.28883500	-2.31997600	-1.73229700
C	3.19695800	1.10408700	1.94837600
O	1.62695300	-2.88594800	-2.59226900
O	2.94561900	2.04607000	2.68808000
O	3.58503700	-2.66230300	-1.49451300
O	4.44601100	0.56569700	1.89106400
C	4.14421000	-3.72584500	-2.30061700
H	4.07545800	-3.44401300	-3.35377900
H	3.54944800	-4.63029000	-2.15416100
C	5.58284100	-3.92603900	-1.86810200
H	6.03365700	-4.72521600	-2.46211500
H	6.16894300	-3.01635800	-2.01857300
H	5.64122100	-4.20903100	-0.81446200
C	5.44892000	1.13635200	2.76454700
H	5.54735200	2.20108300	2.54084200
H	5.11391100	1.03934000	3.79975300
C	6.74770600	0.39276400	2.52520800
H	7.52695400	0.80309100	3.17259500
H	6.63964200	-0.67046900	2.75230700
H	7.07491100	0.49714900	1.48805900
C	-3.40149500	2.24525400	-0.42631100
H	-4.46070002	2.30991722	-0.22555397

Configuration A (Figure 8) – cartesian coordinates

N	-5.970000	-4.457000	1.993000
C	-6.103000	-3.993000	0.693000
C	-5.029000	-3.714000	-0.171000
C	-3.647000	-3.865000	0.163000
C	-2.645000	-3.606000	-0.764000
C	-2.940000	-3.169000	-2.060000
C	-4.292000	-3.000000	-2.408000
C	-5.303000	-3.267000	-1.503000
C	-6.940000	-5.135000	2.724000
C	-6.636000	-5.600000	4.016000
C	-7.558000	-6.317000	4.773000
C	-8.831000	-6.585000	4.257000
C	-9.147000	-6.130000	2.976000
C	-8.222000	-5.423000	2.215000
H	-5.656000	-5.399000	4.437000
H	-7.269000	-6.655000	5.759000
H	-10.129000	-6.345000	2.569000
H	-8.502000	-5.110000	1.218000
H	-3.356000	-4.206000	1.152000
H	-6.341000	-3.162000	-1.813000
H	-1.610000	-3.747000	-0.466000
H	-4.554000	-2.667000	-3.408000
H	-2.151000	-2.971000	-2.777000
H	-7.103000	-3.859000	0.332000
O	-9.817000	-7.279000	4.921000
C	-9.524000	-7.775000	6.225000
H	-9.286000	-6.963000	6.919000
H	-10.426000	-8.284000	6.562000
H	-8.694000	-8.489000	6.204000
H	-5.045000	-4.443000	2.399000
C	-7.470000	-2.782000	6.141000
C	-8.367000	-2.648000	5.097000
C	-7.899000	-2.262000	3.810000
N	-6.572000	-1.854000	3.773000
C	-5.671000	-1.912000	4.771000
C	-6.101000	-2.377000	6.023000
C	-8.709000	-1.818000	2.633000
C	-4.300000	-1.422000	4.430000
C	-9.825000	-2.891000	5.310000

O	-10.131000	-3.125000	6.592000
C	-11.537000	-3.348000	6.907000
C	-11.641000	-3.562000	8.401000
C	-5.175000	-2.511000	7.157000
O	-5.818000	-2.888000	8.283000
C	-5.002000	-3.105000	9.466000
C	-5.924000	-3.539000	10.586000
O	-10.658000	-2.840000	4.423000
O	-3.966000	-2.327000	7.123000
H	-3.601000	-2.260000	4.418000
H	-4.294000	-0.946000	3.448000
H	-3.938000	-0.717000	5.178000
H	-8.052000	-1.590000	1.789000
H	-9.424000	-2.576000	2.316000
H	-9.283000	-0.912000	2.864000
H	-11.876000	-4.219000	6.343000
H	-12.100000	-2.472000	6.579000
H	-12.688000	-3.731000	8.667000
H	-11.064000	-4.435000	8.712000
H	-11.287000	-2.687000	8.950000
H	-4.255000	-3.868000	9.235000
H	-4.482000	-2.175000	9.705000
H	-5.336000	-3.708000	11.492000
H	-6.670000	-2.770000	10.802000
H	-6.439000	-4.469000	10.335000
H	-6.243000	-1.482000	2.891000
H	-7.826000	-3.123000	7.103000

Hantzsch ester (4a) – cartesian coordinates

C	-3.06402100	1.67582000	3.09817900
C	-0.83685500	2.19487800	2.20713800
C	-3.47383300	2.96413600	2.94107900
C	-1.17018900	3.50053000	2.01630800
C	-2.50498200	4.05077100	2.49808700
H	-2.96270800	4.64411600	1.70320900
H	-2.34174900	4.76310800	3.31764800
C	0.45864900	1.52607000	1.83744300
C	-3.89251500	0.51486600	3.57677500
H	-3.25941700	-0.35393400	3.76806600
H	-4.43504800	0.76627800	4.48652200
H	-4.63916500	0.23984200	2.82869300
C	-4.85658800	3.34644200	3.23597600
C	-0.23170100	4.42420500	1.37362700
O	-5.77771200	2.60554700	3.55296500
O	0.84666600	4.14901500	0.86448500
O	-5.03130200	4.68749100	3.11799700
O	-0.70307600	5.69674400	1.39567400
C	-6.36003600	5.20382500	3.37723800
H	-6.64921300	4.93254300	4.39486000
H	-7.06148800	4.72905000	2.68767100
C	-6.31560800	6.70621700	3.18770700
H	-7.30670900	7.12563700	3.37872000
H	-5.60935400	7.16940400	3.88071400
H	-6.02574500	6.96595900	2.16690800
C	0.12196100	6.71612000	0.77942200
H	1.09321900	6.73038700	1.27858200
H	0.28277800	6.45086900	-0.26782100
C	-0.60072700	8.04018300	0.91932900
H	-0.00094700	8.83120900	0.46188700
H	-1.57102500	8.01389100	0.41797400
H	-0.75660400	8.29426900	1.97037600
H	0.51807300	1.37345300	0.75701500
H	1.31360100	2.13700200	2.11905000
H	0.53691900	0.55243900	2.32563300
H	-1.48273700	0.38053300	2.91542000
N	-1.75659900	1.34351900	2.79301400

Other structures are available from the corresponding authors upon request.

Table S4. Calculated Absorption Energies (eV, and in the corresponding Wavelength, nm) and oscillator strengths for the different Hantzsch Ester (HE) species and the selected HE complexes.

Molecule	Energy (eV)	Wavelength (nm)	Oscillator strength
HEH(4a) neutral	3.56	348.5	0.2003
HE (4a) anionic	2.96	418.3	0.3013
HEH (4b) neutral	3.55	349.1	0.2068
HE (4b) anionic	2.97	417.0	0.3138
HEH (phenyl) neutral	3.80	326.4	0.1835
HE (phenyl) anionic	3.15	393.1	0.2643
HEH (cyclohexyl) neutral	3.86	321.3	0.1883
HE (cyclohexyl) anionic	3.23	383.4	0.2921
Stacked complex (Figure 3)	2.99	414.1	0.2281
T-shaped complex (Figure 3)	3.50	354.2	0.1999
Configuration A (Figure 8)	2.74	452.6	0.1559

CAM-B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)/DMSO absorption spectra computed for the stacked complex and T-shaped complexes optimized at the B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p) level in DMSO (artificially broadened with gaussian peaks – HWHH = 0.1 eV).

Stacked Complex

Excited State	1:	1.6608 eV	746.51 nm	f=0.0450
Excited State	2:	2.9943 eV	414.07 nm	f=0.2281
Excited State	3:	3.4770 eV	356.58 nm	f=0.7886
Excited State	4:	3.7611 eV	329.65 nm	f=0.0562
Excited State	5:	4.0385 eV	307.00 nm	f=0.0013
Excited State	6:	4.1586 eV	298.14 nm	f=0.0024
Excited State	7:	4.2956 eV	288.63 nm	f=0.0342
Excited State	8:	4.3663 eV	283.96 nm	f=0.0056
Excited State	9:	4.3960 eV	282.04 nm	f=0.0035
Excited State	10:	4.6040 eV	269.29 nm	f=0.0005
Excited State	11:	4.6383 eV	267.30 nm	f=0.0004
Excited State	12:	4.6448 eV	266.93 nm	f=0.0021
Excited State	13:	4.6957 eV	264.04 nm	f=0.0101
Excited State	14:	4.8666 eV	254.77 nm	f=0.0009
Excited State	15:	4.9189 eV	252.06 nm	f=0.0594

H-bonded Complex

Excited State	1:	3.5177 eV	352.46 nm	f=0.2001
Excited State	2:	3.9351 eV	315.08 nm	f=0.5841
Excited State	3:	4.4153 eV	280.80 nm	f=0.0016
Excited State	4:	4.8173 eV	257.37 nm	f=0.0488
Excited State	5:	4.9100 eV	252.51 nm	f=0.0275
Excited State	6:	4.9210 eV	251.95 nm	f=0.3377
Excited State	7:	5.1341 eV	241.49 nm	f=0.0002
Excited State	8:	5.1844 eV	239.15 nm	f=0.0012
Excited State	9:	5.3771 eV	230.58 nm	f=0.0002
Excited State	10:	5.4469 eV	227.62 nm	f=0.2428
Excited State	11:	5.4915 eV	225.77 nm	f=0.0669
Excited State	12:	5.5041 eV	225.26 nm	f=0.2388
Excited State	13:	5.7408 eV	215.97 nm	f=0.0754
Excited State	14:	5.7892 eV	214.16 nm	f=0.0736
Excited State	15:	5.8266 eV	212.79 nm	f=0.3474

M062X/6-311+G(d,p)/DMSO absorption spectra computed for the stacked complex and T-shaped complexes optimized at the B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p) level in DMSO (artificially broadened with gaussian peaks – HWHH = 0.15 eV).

B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)/DMSO absorption spectra computed for the stacked complex and T-shaped complexes optimized at the **B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)** level in DMSO (artificially broadened with gaussian peaks – HWHH = 0.15 eV).

CAM-B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)/DMSO absorption spectra computed for HEH (4a) and HE (4a) optimized at the **B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)** level in DMSO (artificially broadened with gaussian peaks – HWHH = 0.15 eV).

1.5.2 NEB calculations

To disclose possible minimum-energy paths (MEPs) for the cyclization reactions and estimate the activation energies (transition states -TS) that could be connected to the experimental yield, we used the nudged elastic band (NEB) methodology^[8] implemented in the Quantum Espresso^[9] software package. The calculations were based on a plane-wave basis set; the projector augmented wave (PAW) method with Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) functional, and kinetic energy cutoffs of 40 Ry and 400 Ry for the wave functions and the charge density, respectively. Single-particle wave functions were calculated through Gaussian smearing of 0.002 Ry. The Brillouin zone sampling was restricted to the gamma point, and all the calculations were spin-polarized. Long-range nonlocal effects were included by applying van der Waals corrections (Grimme-D2 approach).

The energy barriers were estimated considering 8-15 intermediate images between the identified local minima, and a convergence cutoff of 0.05 eV Å⁻¹ for the force orthogonal to the path was employed.

After activating the molecules through the blue light (which induces the formation of two radicals, as described above), sets of NEB calculations were carried out to disclose the steps of cyclization. The central panels of **Figures S13-S14** show the energy profiles along the different reaction paths and the structure of the transition states, whereas the left and right panels display the geometries of reactants and products, respectively. In **Table S5**, we have reported energy barriers and final energies relative to the starting configuration of the different complexes.

As shown in **Figure S13-S14**, in the starting configurations, the two radicals are rotated with respect to each other, and the HE is near the aldehydic side chain, pointing its ring hydrogens to the C atom connected to the CO₂Me group. During cyclization, one of these Hs is transferred to that C, and the other carbon atom close by gets close to the ring, forming a bond with the radical carbon of the molecule. Eight steps were required to form the final products in all cases, and the energy barriers were relatively low (at most 10 kcal/mol) and in line with the yield results obtained with experiments.

Figure S13. Cyclization of compound 7 from NEB calculations. (a) 7a; (b) 7c; (c) 7b.

Figure S14. Cyclization of compound 7 from NEB calculations. (a) 7d; (b) 7f; (c) 7e.

Table S5. Energy barriers (TS) and final energy differences (Products) relative to the starting configuration of the different complexes (Figures S13-S14).

compound	Reactant (kcal/mol)	TS (kcal/mol)	Products (kcal/mol)
7a	0	4.2	-55.1
7b	0	3.8	-53.1
7c	0	7.0	-57.2
7d	0	5.1	-56.0
7e	0	10.4	-51.2
7f	0	1.1	-62.1

1.6 Experiments

1.6.1 Photocatalytic reaction setup

The inner surface of a round glass dish with a diameter of 140 mm was fixed with a blue LED strip with a total power of 24 W (Figure S15). A switch can control the intensity of illumination. An electric fan was placed over the glass dish to avoid heating by the LED irradiation. Inside the glass dish, two Schlenk flasks were placed. The reaction mixture was stirred using a magnetic stirring plate and stirring bar at 400 rpm on average.

Figure S15. Setup for visible-light-mediated photocatalytic reactions under N₂ with an electric fan.

1.6.2 General procedure for the three-component coupling

A dried Schlenk flask with magnetic stirring bar was charged with [amine] (0.2 mmol, 1 equiv.) and [Hantzsch ester] (0.3 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), after which the vessel was evacuated using Schlenk techniques and flushed with N₂ three times. Under nitrogen gas flow, [aldehyde (if liquid, otherwise added before flushing cycle)] (0.2 mmol, 1 equiv.), [Michael acceptor (if liquid, otherwise added before flushing cycle)] (0.4 mmol, 2 equiv.), dry DMSO (0.5 mL), and dry CH₂Cl₂ (0.5 mL) were added using a syringe

flushed with inert gas. The resulting mixture was stirred for 24 h under irradiation of blue LED light (24 W) at room temperature. After 24 h, the reaction mixture was quenched by adding distilled water (3 mL) and ethyl acetate (3 mL). The organic phase was extracted and concentrated in vacuo. 1,3,5-Trimethoxybenzene was added as internal standard to determine the NMR yield of the functionalised product through ^1H NMR. Purification proceeded via flash column chromatography.

1.6.3 General procedure for the cyclization reaction

A dried Schlenk flask with magnetic stirring bar was charged with [amine] (0.2 mmol, 1 equiv.) and [Hantzsch ester] (0.3 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), and [aldehyde/olefin substrate] (0.2 mmol, 1 equiv.) after which the vessel was evacuated using Schlenk techniques and flushed with N_2 three times. Under nitrogen gas flow, dry DMSO (0.5 mL), and dry CH_2Cl_2 (0.5 mL) were added using a syringe flushed with inert gas. The resulting mixture was stirred for 24 h under irradiation of blue LED light (24 W) at room temperature. After 24 h, the reaction mixture was quenched by adding distilled water (3 mL) and ethyl acetate (3 mL). The organic phase was extracted and concentrated in vacuo. 1,3,5-Trimethoxybenzene was added as internal standard to determine the NMR yield of the functionalised product through ^1H NMR. Purification proceeded via flash column chromatography.

1.6.4 General procedure for the synthesis of cyclization aldehyde/olefin substrates

A dried two-necked flask with stirring bar was charged with fresh magnesium (1.1 equiv.) and iodine (0.03 mol%), after which the vessel was evacuated and the solid mixtures were vigorously stirred for 10 minutes. A solution of 1-bromo-2-

(dimethoxymethyl)benzene (**SM1**, 1 equiv.) in anhydrous THF (1.6 M) was added dropwise over 15 minutes. The mixture was allowed to stir for further 30 minutes and cool to $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, followed by the dropwise addition of allyl bromide (1 equiv.) over 15 minutes. After that, the solution was allowed to warm to room temperature and stir overnight. The mixture was then quenched with saturated aqueous NH_4Cl solution and stirred for 10 minutes. The product was extracted with EtOAc and washed with H_2O and brine. The combined organic phase was dried with MgSO_4 , followed by filtration and concentration in vacuo. The pure product **SM2** as a colorless oil was obtained via distillation under reduced pressure ($67\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 0.5 mbar).

A dried two-necked flask with stirring bar was charged with **SM2** (1 equiv.) and alkyl acrylate (1.1 equiv.), after which the vessel was evacuated using Schlenk techniques and flushed with N_2 three times. The mixture was dissolved in anhydrous DCM (0.2 M) and warmed to $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. A solution of Hoveyda-Grubbs 2nd Generation catalyst (0.3 mol%) in anhydrous toluene (10^{-3} M) was added dropwise over 1 h. After reaction, the solvent was evaporated in vacuo and the residue was dissolved in conc. HCl (20 mol%) and acetone (0.25 M). After further stirring for 10 minutes, the reaction mixture was quenched with aqueous Na_2CO_3 (1 M), followed by evaporation of acetone in vacuo. The crude product was extracted with EtOAc and washed with H_2O and brine. The combined organic phase was dried with MgSO_4 , followed by filtration and concentration in vacuo. Flash column chromatography was applied to obtain pure product **SM3**.

1.6.5 General procedure for the reductive functionalization with pre-formed imine

A dried Schlenk flask with magnetic stirring bar was charged with [imine] (0.2 mmol, 1 equiv.) and [Hantzsch ester] (0.3 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), after which the vessel was evacuated using Schlenk techniques and flushed with N_2 three times. Under nitrogen gas flow, [Michael acceptor (if liquid, otherwise added before flushing cycle)] (0.4

mmol, 2 equiv.) and dry DMSO (1 mL) were added using a syringe flushed with inert gas. The resulting mixture was stirred for 24 h under irradiation of blue LED light (24 W) at room temperature. After 24 h, the reaction mixture was quenched by adding distilled water (3 mL) and ethyl acetate (3 mL). The organic phase was extracted and concentrated in vacuo. 1,3,5-Trimethoxybenzene was added as internal standard to determine the NMR yield of the functionalised product through ^1H NMR. Purification proceeded via flash column chromatography.

1.6.6 General procedure for synthesis of imines

A dried two-necked flask with stirring bar was charged with [amine (if solid, otherwise added after flushing cycle)] (2 mmol, 1 equiv.) and MgSO_4 (960 mg, 8 mmol, 4 equiv.), after which the vessel was evacuated using Schlenk techniques and flushed with N_2 three times. Under nitrogen gas flow, [aldehyde (if liquid, otherwise added before flushing cycle)] (2 mmol, 1 equiv.) and CH_2Cl_2 (8 mL) were added using a syringe flushed with inert gas. The resulting mixture was stirred for 2 h (unless explicitly stated otherwise) at room temperature. After 2 h, the mixture was filtered over Celite® and concentrated in vacuo. In most cases, the product was dried under high vacuum (< 0.5 mbar) while cooled with liquid nitrogen.

1.6.7 General procedure for synthesis of complex olefins

The following procedure was obtained from literature.¹ Acryloyl chloride (217 mg, 2.4 mmol, 1.2 equiv.) was added to a stirred solution of [complex alcohol] (2 mmol, 1 equiv.), triethylamine (417 μL , 3 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) in DCM (7 mL) at 0 °C. The reaction was warmed to room temperature and stirred for 2 hours. The solvent was removed in vacuo and the residue was purified by flash chromatography (silica, EtOAc in heeptane). Ultimately, the desired fractions were collected and concentrated in vacuo.

1.7 Characterization

*N*¹,*N*²-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,2-diphenylethane-1,2-diamine

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and *n*-butyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 29 μ L). The dimer by-product was observed and purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent

system. **Yield:** 20 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.21-7.16 (m, 6H), 7.15-7.09 (m, 2H), 6.94 (dd, *J* = 6.4, 2.9 Hz, 2H), 6.66 (dd, *J* = 7.7, 5.5 Hz, 4H), 6.47 (dd, *J* = 8.7, 6.1 Hz, 4H), 4.86 (s, 1H), 4.45 (s, 1H), 4.33 (s, 2H), 3.67 (d, *J* = 3.2 Hz, 6H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 158.4, 152.5, 152.3, 141.3, 140.7, 140.3, 138.7, 131.0, 128.7, 128.6, 128.34, 128.2, 127.6, 127.5, 127.4, 122.2, 115.5, 115.1, 114.9, 114.8, 114.4, 65.0, 62.9, 55.7 ppm.

4-((4-Methoxyphenyl)amino)-4-(2,4,6-trimethoxyphenyl)butanenitrile-2-d **5s-D**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), 2,4,6-trimethoxybenzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 39.2 mg), acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μ L), and **4d** as the sole

photoreductant. The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 77 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.73-6.66 (m, 2H), 6.64-6.58 (m, 2H), 6.08 (s, 2H), 5.00 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 1H), 3.83 (s, 6H), 3.76 (s, 3H), 3.69 (s, 3H), 2.47-2.22 (m, 2H), 2.18-1.99 (m, 1H) ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, *m/z*) [M+H⁺] calcd. for C₂₀H₂₃N₂O₄D 358.1872, found 358.1883.

Diethyl 2,6-dimethylpyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate-4-d

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), 2,4,6-trimethoxybenzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 39.2 mg), acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μ L), and **4d** as the sole photoreductant. The crude product

was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 70 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 4.40 (q, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 4H), 2.85 (s, 6H), 1.42 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 6H) ppm.

Diethyl 2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate-1-d 4c

According to the literature ^[10], a dried two-necked flask with stirring bar was charged with diethyl 2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate, after which the vessel was evacuated using Schlenk

techniques and flushed with argon three times. CD₃OD (0.3 M) was added and stirred overnight. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the desired compound was obtained as a pale green solid. **Yield:** 95 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 4.17 (dd, *J* = 13.4, 6.5 Hz, 4H), 3.27 (s, 2H), 2.19 (s, 6H), 1.28 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 6H) ppm.

Diethyl 2,6-dimethylpyridine-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate-4,4-d₂ 4d

According to the literature ^[10], a dried two-necked flask with stirring bar was charged with ethyl acetoacetate (4 equiv.), d₂-

paraformaldehyde (1 equiv.) and ammonium acetate (2 equiv.), after which the vessel was evacuated using Schlenk techniques and flushed with N₂ three times. Then, water (0.15 M) was added and stirred at 90 °C for 3 h. Later, the mixture was cooled to room temperature and filtered, followed by evaporation in vacuo and the desired product was obtained as a yellow solid. **Yield:** 44 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 5.08 (s, 1H), 4.17 (q, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 4H), 2.19 (s, 6H), 1.28 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 6H) ppm.

Diethyl 1,2,6-trimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate 4e

According to the literature ^[11], a dried two-necked flask with stirring bar was charged with Hantzsch ester, after which the vessel was

evacuated using Schlenk techniques and flushed with argon three times. The solid was dissolved in anhydrous THF (0.11 M) and stirred at 0 °C, followed by the addition of sodium hydride. After further stirring for 10 minutes, iodomethane was dropwise added. The reaction mixture was warmed to room temperature and stirred for 15 minutes. Later, the mixture was refluxed overnight. The addition of water and extraction of EtOAc were required and combined organic phases were dried with MgSO₄. Purification proceeded via flash column chromatography (heptane/ethyl acetate as eluent). **Yield:** 54 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 4.18 (q, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 4H), 3.15 (m, 5H), 2.38 (s, 6H), 1.29 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 6H) ppm.

4-Methoxy-N-(phenylmethyl-d)aniline

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), and benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L). The green LED (90 W, 525 nm) was used instead of blue LED. The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 34 %. **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.41 – 7.22 (m, 5H), 6.77 (d, $J = 8.9$ Hz, 2H), 6.60 (d, $J = 8.9$ Hz, 2H), 4.26 (s, 1H), 3.74 (s, 3H).

Methyl 2-(bis(*t*-butoxycarbonyl)amino)acrylate **3ai**

According to the literature ^[12], the desired product can be obtained in 36 % yield over three steps. **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 6.34 (s, 1H), 5.64 (s, 1H), 3.79 (s, 3H), 1.47 (s, 18H) ppm.

13-Methyl-17-oxo-7,8,9,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-decahydro-6H-cyclopenta[*a*]phenantren-3-yl acrylate **3am**

Following procedure 1.6.7 with estrone (2 mmol, 540.8 mg). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 54 %. **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.29 (t, $J = 6.9$ Hz, 1H), 6.95-6.82 (m, 2H), 6.59 (d, $J = 17.3$ Hz, 1H), 6.31 (dd, $J = 17.3, 10.4$ Hz, 1H), 5.99 (d, $J = 10.4$ Hz, 1H), 2.98-2.87 (m, 2H), 2.51 (dd, $J = 18.8, 8.6$ Hz, 1H), 2.40 (m, 1H), 2.31 (m, 1H), 2.20-1.94 (m, 4H), 1.69-1.41 (m, 6H), 0.91 (s, 3H).

2,5,7,8-tetramethyl-2-(4,8,12-trimethyltridecyl)chroman-6-yl acrylate **3an**

Following procedure 1.6.7 with 2,5,7,8-tetramethyl-2-(4,8,12-trimethyltridecyl)chroman-6-ol (2 mmol, 861.4 mg). The crude product was

purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 66 %. **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 6.62 (dd, $J = 17.3, 1.2$ Hz, 1H), 6.37 (dd, $J = 17.3, 10.4$ Hz, 1H), 6.00 (dd, $J = 10.5, 1.2$ Hz, 1H), 2.59 (t, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 2H), 2.09 (s, 3H), 2.01 (s, 3H), 1.97 (s, 3H), 1.88-1.70 (m, 2H), 1.63-1.45 (m, 2H), 1.43-1.34 (m, 3H), 1.33-0.99 (m, 19H), 0.86 (dd, $J = 8.9, 6.1$ Hz, 12H) ppm.

2-(Acetoxymethyl)-6-(2-(acryloyloxy)ethoxy)tetrahydro-2H-pyran-3,4,5-triyl triacetate **3ao**

Following procedure 1.6.7 with 2-(acetoxymethyl)-6-(2-hydroxyethoxy)tetrahydro-2H-pyran-3,4,5-triyl triacetate (2 mmol, 784.8 mg. The crude product was purified using flash

column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 78 %. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 6.43 (dd, $J = 17.3, 1.4$ Hz, 1H), 6.14 (dd, $J = 17.3, 10.4$ Hz, 1H), 5.86 (dd, $J = 10.4, 1.4$ Hz, 1H), 5.42-5.36 (m, 1H), 5.22 (dd, $J = 10.5, 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 5.02 (dd, $J = 10.5, 3.4$ Hz, 1H), 4.53 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 4.38-4.25 (m, 2H), 4.22-4.10 (m, 2H), 4.09-4.01 (m, 1H), 3.91 (td, $J = 6.6, 0.9$ Hz, 1H), 3.86-3.79 (m, 1H), 2.15 (s, 3H), 2.05 (s, 3H), 2.03 (s, 3H), 1.98 (s, 3H) ppm.

(10S,13R,16S)-10,13-Dimethyl-3-oxohexadecahydro-1H-cyclopenta[a]phenanthren-16-yl acrylate **3aq**

Following procedure 1.6.7 with (10S,13R,16S)-16-hydroxy-10,13-dimethylhexadecahydro-3H-cyclopenta[a]phenanthren-3-one (2 mmol, 580.8 mg. The

crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 36 %. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 6.37 (d, $J = 17.3$ Hz, 1H), 6.11 (dd, $J = 17.3, 10.4$ Hz, 1H), 5.80 (d, $J = 10.4$ Hz, 1H), 4.68 (t, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 2.46-1.96 (m, 6H), 1.81-1.61 (m, 4H), 1.57-1.06 (m, 10H), 1.02 (s, 3H), 0.93 (ddd, $J = 25.0, 12.5, 5.4$ Hz, 1H), 0.84 (s, 3H), 0.80-0.71 (m, 1H) ppm.

1-Allyl-2-(dimethoxymethyl)benzene **SM2**

Following procedure 1.6.4 with 1-Allyl-2-(dimethoxymethyl)benzene (2 mmol, 580.8 mg. The crude product was purified using distillation under

reduced pressure. **Yield:** 56 %. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ = 7.58 (dd, $J = 7.4, 1.6$, 1H), 7.34 -7.18 (m, 3H), 6.04-5.93 (m, 1H), 5.47 (s, 1H), 5.17-4.97 (m, 2H), 3.54 (m, 2H), 3.35 (s, 6H).

Methyl (E)-4-(2-formylphenyl)but-2-enoate **6a**

Following procedure 1.6.4 with **SM2** (1 equiv.) and methyl acrylate (1.1 equiv.). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 53 %. $^1\text{H NMR}$

(400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 10.15 (s, 1H), 7.83 (d, J = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 7.55 (t, J = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.46 (t, J = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.27 (d, J = 8.2 Hz, 1H), 7.14 (dt, J = 15.6, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 5.73 (dd, J = 15.7, 1.5 Hz, 1H), 3.98 (d, J = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 3.70 (s, 3H).

tert-Butyl (*E*)-4-(2-formylphenyl)but-2-enoate **6b**

Following procedure 1.6.4 with **SM2** (1 equiv.) and *tert*-butyl acrylate (1.1 equiv.). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 75 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 10.17 (s, 1H), 7.84 (dd, J = 7.6, 1.1 Hz, 1H), 7.55 (td, J = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 7.45 (t, J = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.28 (s, 1H), 7.02 (dt, J = 15.6, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 5.63 (dt, J = 15.6, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 3.95 (dd, J = 6.4, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 1.45 (s, 9H).

Butyl 4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)-4-phenylbutanoate **5a**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and *n*-butyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 29 μ L). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 63 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.32-7.19 (m, 5H), 6.69-6.67 (m, 2H), 6.49-6.46 (m, 2H), 4.32-4.29 (t, J = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 4.09-4.05 (t, J = 6.7 Hz, 2H), 3.69 (s, 3H), 2.41-2.38 (t, J = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 2.14-2.09 (m, 2H), 1.61-1.57 (m, 2H), 1.39-1.33 (m, 2H), 0.94-0.90 (t, J = 7.4 Hz, 3H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.7, 152.1, 143.4, 141.4, 128.7, 127.2, 126.5, 114.8, 114.6, 64.5, 58.7, 55.8, 33.3, 31.3, 30.7, 19.1, 13.7 ppm.

Butyl 4-((4-(*t*-butyl)phenyl)amino)-4-phenylbutanoate **5b**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-*t*-butylaniline (0.2 mmol, 32 μ L), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and *n*-butyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 29 μ L). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 54 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.35-7.31 (m, 4H), 7.22 (t, J = 6.9 Hz, 1H), 7.10 (d, J = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 6.47 (d, J = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 4.34 (t, J = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 4.18 (s, 1H), 4.06 (t, J = 6.7 Hz, 2H), 2.39 (t, J = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 2.10 (dt, J = 13.7, 7.2 Hz, 2H), 1.64-1.53 (m, 2H), 1.36 (m, 2H), 1.22 (s, 9H), 0.92 (t, J = 7.4 Hz, 3H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.7, 144.9, 143.6, 140.0, 128.7,

127.1, 126.4, 125.9, 112.9, 64.5, 58.1, 33.8, 33.4, 31.5, 31.3, 30.7, 19.1, 13.7 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, *m/z*) [M+H⁺] calcd. for C₂₄H₃₃NO₂ 368.2584, found 368.2728.

Butyl 4-((4-fluorophenyl)amino)-4-phenylbutanoate 5c

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-fluoroaniline (0.2 mmol, 19 μ L), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and *n*-butyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 29 μ L). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 47 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.32-7.18 (m, 5H), 6.80-6.75 (m, 2H), 6.45-6.41 (m, 2H), 4.32-4.29 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 4.09-4.05 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 2H), 2.41-2.38 (t, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 2H), 2.17-2.07 (m, 2H), 1.61-1.57 (m, 2H), 1.38-1.33 (m, 2H), 0.94-0.90 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 3H) ppm. **¹⁹F NMR** (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -128.22 ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.7, 143.0, 128.8, 127.3, 126.4, 115.6, 115.4, 114.2, 114.1, 64.6, 58.5, 33.3, 31.3, 30.7, 19.1, 13.7 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, *m/z*) [M+H⁺] calcd. for C₂₀H₂₄NO₂F 330.1864, found 330.1878.

Methyl 4-((4-butoxy-4-oxo-1-phenylbutyl)amino)benzoate 5d

Following procedure 1.6.2 with methyl 4-aminobenzoate (0.2 mmol, 30.2 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and *n*-butyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 29 μ L). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 62 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.77 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.38-7.27 (m, 4H), 7.25-7.19 (m, 1H), 6.48 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.87 (d, *J* = 5.9 Hz, 1H), 4.46 (dd, *J* = 13.3, 6.2 Hz, 1H), 4.09 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 2H), 3.81 (s, 3H), 2.41 (td, *J* = 6.9, 2.0 Hz, 2H), 2.27-2.00 (m, 2H), 1.67-1.50 (m, 2H), 1.36 (dd, *J* = 15.0, 7.5 Hz, 2H), 0.92 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 3H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.7, 167.2, 151.0, 142.2, 131.4, 128.9, 127.5, 126.28, 118.6, 112.2, 64.7, 57.6, 51.5, 32.9, 31.2, 30.7, 19.1, 13.7 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, *m/z*) [M+H⁺] calcd. for C₂₂H₂₇NO₄ 370.2013, found 370.2016.

Butyl 4-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)-4-phenylbutanoate 5e

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-(trifluoromethyl)aniline (0.2 mmol, 25 μ L), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and *n*-butyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 29 μ L). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 62%. **¹H NMR**

(400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.34-7.21 (m, 7H), 6.51 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 4.76 (s, 1H), 4.41 (dd, *J* = 12.2, 5.7 Hz, 1H), 4.08 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 2H), 2.41 (td, *J* = 6.9, 3.5 Hz, 2H), 2.26-2.04 (m, 2H), 1.59 (dt, *J* = 14.6, 6.8 Hz, 2H), 1.43-1.27 (m, 2H), 0.92 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 3H) ppm. **¹⁹F NMR** (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -61.11 ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.7, 149.7, 142.3, 128.9, 127.5, 126.5, 126.5, 126.3, 119.1-118.8 (d, CF₃), 112.5, 64.7, 57.7, 32.9, 31.2, 30.7, 19.1, 13.7 ppm.

4-((4-Methoxyphenyl)amino)-4-phenylbutanenitrile **5f**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μL), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL). The crude product was purified using flash column

chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 67%. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.35-7.29 (m, 4H), 7.28-7.22 (m, 1H), 6.73-6.63 (m, 2H), 6.53 (dd, *J* = 9.6, 2.7 Hz, 2H), 4.41 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 1H), 3.68 (s, 3H), 2.49-2.25 (m, 2H), 2.23-1.95 (m, 2H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 152.6, 141.9, 140.7, 129.0, 127.8, 126.3, 119.4, 115.3, 114.9, 57.9, 55.7, 33.6, 14.5 ppm.

4-((4-Ethynylphenyl)amino)-4-phenylbutanenitrile **5g**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-ethynylaniline (0.2 mmol, 23.4 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μL), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL). The crude product was purified using flash column

chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 34%. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.39-7.27 (m, 5H), 7.23 (m, 2H), 6.49 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 4.51 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 4.19 (s, 1H), 2.92 (s, 1H), 2.52-2.29 (m, 2H), 2.26-2.00 (m, 2H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 146.9, 141.0, 133.4, 129.2, 128.1, 126.3, 119.1, 113.3, 111.1, 84.3, 75.0, 56.8, 33.4, 14.5 ppm.

4-(Mesitylamino)-4-phenylbutanenitrile **5h**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 2,4,6-trimethylaniline (0.2 mmol, 28 μL), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μL), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL). The crude product was purified using flash column

chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 77%. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.32-7.26 (m, 3H), 7.15 (dd, *J* = 7.7, 1.5 Hz, 2H), 6.75 (s, 2H), 4.11 (dt, *J* =

6.5, 4.0 Hz, 1H), 2.49-2.38 (m, 1H), 2.33 (ddt, $J = 18.3, 11.7, 4.7$ Hz, 2H), 2.19 (s, 3H), 2.18-2.11 (m, 1H), 2.09 (s, 6H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 141.9, 141.1, 131.7, 130.1, 129.6, 128.9, 127.9, 126.6, 119.4, 60.8, 31.9, 20.5, 18.7, 14.9 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺, m/z) [$\text{M}+\text{H}^+$] calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2$ 279.1856, found 279.1847.

4-Phenyl-4-(*p*-tolylamino)butanenitrile **5i**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-toluidine (0.2 mmol, 21.4 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μL), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 67%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.39-7.28 (m, 4H), 7.29-7.19 (m, 1H), 6.92 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 2H), 6.50 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 4.47 (t, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.53-2.30 (m, 2H), 2.26-2.05 (m, 5H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 144.3, 141.8, 129.8, 129.0, 127.8, 127.5, 126.3, 119.3, 113.9, 57.3, 33.6, 20.3, 14.5 ppm.

4-((4-Benzylphenyl)amino)-4-phenylbutanenitrile **5j**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-benzylaniline (0.2 mmol, 36.7 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μL), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 78%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.38-7.30 (m, 4H), 7.28 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.23 (d, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 7.19-7.10 (m, 3H), 6.93 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 2H), 6.51 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 2H), 4.46 (t, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 1H), 4.00 (s, 1H), 3.82 (s, 2H), 2.50-2.27 (m, 2H), 2.24-2.02 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 144.8, 141.8, 141.7, 130.9, 129.7, 129.0, 128.8, 128.4, 127.8, 126.3, 125.9, 119.3, 113.9, 57.2, 41.0, 33.6, 14.5 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺, m/z) [$\text{M}+\text{H}^+$] calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2$ 327.1856, found 327.1852.

4-((4-Hydroxyphenyl)amino)-4-phenylbutanenitrile **5k**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-aminophenol (0.2 mmol, 21.8 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μL), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 85%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.38-7.26 (m, 4H), 7.25-7.22 (m, 1H), 6.66-6.57 (m, 2H), 6.49 (dd, $J = 9.4$,

2.7 Hz, 2H), 4.40 (t, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 1H), 4.07 (m, 2H), 2.51-2.29 (m, 2H), 2.23-2.00 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 148.2, 141.8, 140.7, 129.0, 127.8, 126.3, 119.4, 116.2, 115.5, 58.0, 33.6, 14.5 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺, m/z) [$\text{M}+\text{H}^+$] calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ 253.1335, found 253.1335.

4-Phenyl-4-(phenylamino)butanenitrile **5l**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with aniline (0.2 mmol, 18 μL), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μL), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL).

The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 83%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.38-7.23 (m, 5H), 7.11 (dd, $J = 8.4, 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 6.69 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 1H), 6.57 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H), 4.50 (t, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 1H), 4.00 (s, 1H), 2.55-2.27 (m, 2H), 2.23-1.92 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 146.6, 141.6, 129.3, 129.0, 127.8, 126.3, 119.3, 118.2, 113.7, 57.0, 33.6, 14.5 ppm.

4-((4-(1H-Pyrrol-1-yl)amino)-4-phenylbutanenitrile **5m**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)aniline (0.2 mmol, 31.6 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μL), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent

system. **Yield:** 56%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.41-7.26 (m, 5H), 7.13 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 2H), 6.91 (t, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 2H), 6.60 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 2H), 6.26 (t, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 2H), 4.49 (t, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 1H), 4.08 (s, 1H), 2.53-2.28 (m, 2H), 2.28-2.01 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 144.8, 141.4, 132.6, 129.1, 128.0, 126.3, 122.4, 119.6, 119.2, 114.3, 109.4, 57.3, 33.6, 14.5 ppm.

4-((3-Cyano-1-phenylpropyl)amino)benzonitrile **5n**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-aminobenzonitrile (0.2 mmol, 23.6 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μL), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL). The crude product was purified using flash column

chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 89%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.44-7.31 (m, 7H), 6.58 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 4.59 (dt, $J = 20.4, 6.7$ Hz, 2H),

2.52-2.31 (m, 2H), 2.30-2.10 (m, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 149.8, 140.2, 133.7, 129.4, 128.4, 126.2, 120.0, 118.9, 113.3, 100.2, 56.6, 33.2, 14.5 ppm.

Butyl 4-((4-fluorophenyl)-4-(phenylamino)butanoate 5o

Following procedure 1.6.2 with aniline (0.2 mmol, 18 μL), 4-fluorobenzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 21 μL), and *n*-butyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 29 μL). The crude product was purified using flash column

chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 54%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.30 (dd, $J = 8.6, 5.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.08 (dd, $J = 8.4, 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 7.00 (t, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 2H), 6.64 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 1H), 6.48 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H), 4.42-4.28 (t, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 1H), 4.26 (s, 1H), 4.07 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 2H), 2.40 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 2.15-2.03 (m, 2H), 1.59 (dt, $J = 14.7, 6.9$ Hz, 2H), 1.35 (dt, $J = 14.6, 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 0.92 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 3H) ppm. ^{19}F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -115.71 ppm. ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.6, 160.7, 147.0, 138.9, 129.1, 127.9, 127.8, 117.5, 115.7, 115.4, 113.3, 64.6, 57.2, 33.4, 31.2, 30.7, 19.1, 13.7 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI $^+$, m/z) [$\text{M}+\text{H}^+$] calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{NO}_2\text{F}$ 330.1864, found 330,1878.

Butyl 4-((4-methoxyphenyl)-4-(phenylamino)butanoate 5p

Following procedure 1.6.2 with aniline (0.2 mmol, 18 μL), 4-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 24 μL), and *n*-butyl acrylate (0.4 mmol). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation,

4b (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 58%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.25-7.23 (m, 2H), 7.07 (dd, $J = 8.3, 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 6.86-6.84 (m, 2H), 6.64 -6.61(dt, $J = 7.3, 1.0$ Hz, 1H), 6.52-6.50 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H), 4.34-4.31 (t, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 1H), 4.20 (s, 1H), 4.07-4.05 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 2H), 3.77 (s, 3H), 2.38 (t, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 2H), 2.20-1.98 (m, 2H), 1.65-1.48 (m, 2H), 1.43-1.23 (m, 1H), 0.92 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 2H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.7, 158.7, 147.3, 135.2, 129.1, 127.5, 117.3, 114.1, 113.3, 64.5, 57.2, 55.3, 33.3, 31.3, 30.7, 19.1, 13.7 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI $^+$, m/z) [$\text{M}+\text{H}^+$] calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{27}\text{NO}_3$ 342.2064, found 342.2071.

4-(4-Fluorophenyl)-4-(*p*-tolylamino)butanenitrile **5q**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-toluidine (0.2 mmol, 22 μ L), 4-fluorobenzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 21 μ L), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μ L). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For

isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 80%. **^1H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.32-7.26 (m, 1H), 7.02 (dd, J = 12.0, 5.3 Hz, 1H), 6.92 (d, J = 8.2 Hz, 1H), 6.47 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 1H), 4.46 (t, J = 7.0 Hz, 1H), 3.84 (s, 1H), 2.51-2.29 (m, 1H), 2.19 (s, 1H), 2.09 (ddt, J = 32.5, 13.9, 7.0 Hz, 1H) ppm. **^{19}F NMR** (376 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -114.54 ppm. **^{13}C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 163.4, 161.0, 144.1, 137.6, 137.6, 129.8, 127.9, 127.8, 127.7, 119.2, 116.0, 115.8, 114.0, 56.6, 33.7, 20.3, 14.5 ppm.

4-(4-Fluorophenyl)-4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)butanenitrile **5r**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), 4-fluorobenzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 21 μ L), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μ L). The crude product was purified using flash

column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 77%. **^1H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.34-7.25 (m, 2H), 7.02 (t, J = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 6.70 (d, J = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 6.51 (d, J = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 4.41 (t, J = 7.0 Hz, 1H), 3.70 (s, 3H), 2.41 (ddt, J = 50.4, 17.0, 7.1 Hz, 2H), 2.24-1.97 (m, 2H) ppm. **^{19}F NMR** (376 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -114.50 ppm. **^{13}C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 163.4, 161.0, 152.8, 140.4, 137.7, 137.6, 128.0, 127.9, 119.2, 116.0, 115.8, 115.4, 114.9, 57.3, 55.7, 33.7, 14.5 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, m/z) [$\text{M}+\text{H}^+$] calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{OF}$ 285.1398, found 285.1393.

4-((4-Methoxyphenyl)amino)-4-(2,4,6-trimethoxyphenyl)butanenitrile **5s**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), 2,4,6-trimethoxybenzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 39.2 mg), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μ L). The crude product was purified

using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 90%. **^1H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 6.70 (d, J = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 6.62 (d, J = 9.0 Hz, 2H), 6.09 (s, 2H), 5.00 (t, J = 7.4 Hz, 1H), 4.52 (s, 1H), 3.84 (s, 6H), 3.76 (s, 3H), 3.70 (s, 3H), 2.52-2.21 (m, 3H), 2.17-1.84 (m, 1H) ppm. **^{13}C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 160.4, 159.0,

152.2, 142.0, 120.1, 115.3, 114.8, 109.6, 91.0, 55.7, 55.7, 55.3, 48.8, 30.6, 14.8 ppm.

HRMS (ESI⁺, *m/z*) [M+H⁺] calcd. for C₂₀H₂₄N₂O₄ 357.1809, found 357.1797.

4-([1,1'-Biphenyl]-4-yl)-4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)butanenitrile **5t**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), 4-phenylbenzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 36.4 mg), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL). The crude product was purified

using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 57%.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.60-7.52 (m, 4H), 7.38 (qd, *J* = 14.9, 7.3 Hz, 5H), 6.78-6.66 (m, 2H), 6.61-6.49 (m, 2H), 4.47 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 1H), 3.74 (s, 1H), 3.70 (s, 3H), 2.56-2.33 (m, 2H), 2.16 (dtd, *J* = 20.9, 14.0, 6.9 Hz, 2H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 152.7, 140.9, 140.7, 140.6, 140.5, 128.8, 127.7, 127.4, 127.0, 126.8, 119.4, 115.3, 114.9, 57.6, 55.7, 33.6, 14.6 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, *m/z*) [M+H⁺] calcd. for C₂₃H₂₂N₂O₁ 343.1805, found 343.1789.

4-(4-Hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)butanenitrile **5u**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), syringaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 36.4 mg), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL). The crude product was purified using flash column

chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 77%. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.72 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 6.55 (t, *J* = 4.4 Hz, 4H), 5.45 (s, 1H), 4.32 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 1H), 3.87 (s, 6H), 3.71 (s, 3H), 2.64-2.25 (m, 2H), 2.25-1.91 (m, 2H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 152.7, 147.5, 140.8, 134.2, 133.1, 119.4, 115.4, 114.9, 103.0, 58.4, 56.4, 55.7, 33.7, 14.5 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, *m/z*) [M+H⁺] calcd. for C₁₉H₂₂N₂O₄ 343.1652, found 343.1644.

4-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)butanenitrile **5v**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), 4-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 24 μL), and acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL). The crude product was

purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 65%.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.23 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 6.92-6.81 (m, 2H), 6.76-6.66 (m, 2H), 6.54 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 4.37 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 1H), 3.78 (s, 3H), 3.70 (s, 3H), 2.51-2.24 (m, 2H), 2.24-1.98 (m, 2H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 159.1, 152.6, 140.8, 133.8, 127.4, 119.4, 115.3, 114.9, 114.4, 57.4, 55.7, 55.3, 33.6, 14.5 ppm.

4-Cyclohexyl-4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)butanenitrile **5w**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), cyclohexanecarbaldehyde (0.4 mmol, 48 μL), acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL) and additional acetic acid (0.02 mmol, 1.1 μL).

The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 42%. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.76 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 6.56 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 3.74 (s, 3H), 3.31-3.17 (m, 1H), 2.52-2.39 (m, 2H), 2.09-1.91 (m, 1H), 1.74 (s, 3H), 1.66 (dd, *J* = 12.5, 5.1 Hz, 2H), 1.51 (ddd, *J* = 11.7, 8.3, 4.6 Hz, 1H), 1.24-0.99 (m, 5H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 152.1, 142.2, 120.1, 115.1, 114.6, 58.1, 55.8, 42.1, 29.3, 29.0, 28.5, 26.5, 26.3, 26.3, 14.6 ppm.

Butyl 4-cyclohexyl-4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)butanoate **5x**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), cyclohexanecarbaldehyde (0.4 mmol, 48 μL), *n*-butyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 29 μL) and additional acetic acid (0.02 mmol, 1.1 μL). The

crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 25 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.73 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.50 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 4.03 (t, *J* = 6.3 Hz, 2H), 3.73 (s, 3H), 3.19-3.08 (m, 1H), 2.48-2.29 (m, 2H), 2.00-1.86 (m, 1H), 1.74 (d, *J* = 9.5 Hz, 3H), 1.65 (d, *J* = 5.8 Hz, 2H), 1.58-1.46 (m, 4H), 1.32 (dt, *J* = 14.8, 7.5 Hz, 2H), 1.11 (ddd, *J* = 35.8, 16.7, 7.4 Hz, 5H), 0.90 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 3H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 174.2, 151.5, 142.8, 115.0, 114.0, 64.3, 58.5, 55.9, 42.1, 31.7, 30.7, 29.2, 29.0, 27.4, 26.6, 26.5, 26.4, 19.1, 13.7 ppm.

4-Cycloheptyl-4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)butanenitrile **5y**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), cycloheptanecarbaldehyde (0.4 mmol, 52 μL), acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL) and additional acetic acid (0.02 mmol, 1.1 μL).

The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 34 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.77 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 6.57 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 3.75 (s, 3H), 3.29 (dt, *J* = 10.2, 3.6 Hz, 1H), 2.53-2.41 (m, 2H), 2.00-1.86 (m, 1H), 1.77-1.61 (m, 6H), 1.58-1.44 (m, 6H), 1.34 (ddd, *J* = 19.4, 12.2, 5.6 Hz, 2H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 152.2, 141.8, 120.1, 115.1, 114.8, 59.0, 55.8, 42.3, 30.8, 29.6, 28.3, 28.1, 27.9, 27.1, 26.4, 14.9 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, *m/z*) [M+H⁺] calcd. for C₁₈H₂₆N₂O 287.2118, found 287.2132.

t-Butyl 4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)-5-methylhexanoate **5z**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), 2-methylpropanal (0.4 mmol, 36 μL), *t*-butyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 29 μL) and additional acetic acid (0.02 mmol, 1.1 μL).

The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 12 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.74 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 6.51 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 3.73 (s, 3H), 3.23-3.06 (m, 1H), 2.40-2.23 (m, 2H), 1.95-1.77 (m, 2H), 1.61 (m, 1H), 1.42 (s, 9H), 0.93 (d, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 2H), 0.89 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 2H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.4, 151.5, 142.8, 115.0, 114.1, 80.2, 58.9, 55.9, 53.4, 32.8, 31.3, 28.1, 18.6, 18.0 ppm.

5-Ethyl-4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)heptanenitrile **5aa**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), 2-ethylbutanal (0.4 mmol, 50 μL), acrylonitrile (0.4 mmol, 26 μL) and additional acetic acid (0.02 mmol, 1.1 μL). The crude product

was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 17 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.77 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 6.57 (s, 2H), 3.74 (s, 3H), 3.46 (s, 1H), 2.51-2.43 (m, 2H), 1.90 (m, 1H), 1.61 (ddd, *J* = 16.1, 13.6, 6.5 Hz, 1H), 1.40 (dd, *J* = 13.7, 6.4 Hz, 3H), 1.29-1.16 (m, 3H), 0.96 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 3H), 0.89 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 152.2, 141.9, 120.0, 115.1, 114.7, 55.8, 44.5, 29.7, 27.9, 22.5, 22.0, 14.8, 12.1, 12.1 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, *m/z*) [M+H⁺] calcd. for C₁₆H₂₄N₂O 261.1961, found 261.1953.

Methyl 4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)-4-phenylbutanoate **5ab**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and methyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 36 μ L). The crude product was purified using flash column

chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 90%. **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.35-7.27 (m, 4H), 7.23-7.17 (m, 1H), 6.74-6.62 (m, 2H), 6.48 (m, , 2H), 4.30 (t, J = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 3.95 (s, 1H), 3.68 (s, 3H), 3.60 (s, 3H), 2.40 (t, J = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 2.26-1.87 (m, 2H) ppm. **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 174.0, 152.0, 143.3, 141.4, 128.7, 127.2, 126.4, 114.8, 114.6, 58.6, 55.8, 51.7, 33.3, 31.0 ppm.

Ethyl 4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)-4-phenylbutanoate **5ac**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and ethyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 43 μ L). The crude product was purified using flash column

chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 86%. **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.32-7.26 (m, 4H), 7.24-7.22 (m, 1H), 6.70-6.64 (m, 2H), 6.55-6.42 (m, 2H), 4.32-4.28 (t, J = 6.9 Hz 1H), 4.12 (q, J = 7.1 Hz, 2H), 3.97 (s, 1H), 3.68 (s, 3H), 2.39 (t, J = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 2.21-1.94 (m, 2H), 1.24 (t, J = 7.1 Hz, 3H) ppm. **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.6, 152.0, 143.4, 141.5, 128.7, 127.2, 126.5, 114.8, 114.6, 60.5, 58.6, 55.8, 33.3, 31.3, 14.2 ppm.

T-butyl 4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)-4-phenylbutanoate **5ad**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and *t*-butyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 29 μ L). The crude product was purified using flash column

chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 64 %. **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.33-7.27 (m, 4H), 7.21 (ddd, J = 8.5, 5.5, 2.4 Hz, 1H), 6.73-6.60 (m, 2H), 6.53-6.29 (m, 2H), 4.28 (dd, J = 7.4, 6.2 Hz, 1H), 4.04 (s, 1H), 3.68 (s, 3H), 2.31 (dd, J = 10.7, 4.2 Hz, 2H), 2.18-1.94 (m, 2H), 1.44 (s, 9H) ppm. **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.0, 151.9, 143.6, 141.6, 128.6, 127.1, 126.5, 114.8, 114.5, 80.5, 58.7, 55.8, 33.4, 32.5, 28.1 ppm.

4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)-3-phenylpropylbenzonitrile **5ae**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and 4-vinylbenzonitrile (0.4 mmol, 48 μ L). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:**

36 %. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.56 (d, J = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 7.38-7.28 (m, 5H), 7.23 (d, J = 9.1 Hz, 2H), 6.73-6.58 (m, 2H), 6.45 (dd, J = 9.6, 2.8 Hz, 2H), 4.24 (t, J = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 3.84 (s, 1H), 3.69 (s, 3H), 2.86-2.58 (m, 2H), 2.26-1.74 (m, 2H) ppm. $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 152.2, 147.3, 143.5, 141.2, 132.3, 129.2, 128.7, 127.3, 126.4, 119.0, 114.9, 114.7, 110.0, 58.3, 55.7, 39.6, 32.8 ppm.

4-Methoxy-N-(3-(perfluorophenyl)-1-phenylpropyl)aniline **5af**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and 2,3,4,5,6-pentafluorostyrene (0.4 mmol, 55 μ L). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:**

48 %. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.32 (d, J = 4.3 Hz, 4H), 7.23 (m, 1H), 6.70 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.50 (d, J = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 4.32 (t, J = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 3.69 (s, 3H), 2.85 (dt, J = 15.2, 7.7 Hz, 1H), 2.78-2.64 (m, 1H), 2.06 (dd, J = 15.1, 7.6 Hz, 2H) ppm. $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (376 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -144.22, -157.60, -162.71 ppm. $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 152.3, 143.0, 141.2, 128.8, 127.4, 126.4, 114.9, 58.9, 55.7, 37.7, 19.7 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, m/z) [$M+H^+$] calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{NOF}_5$ 408.1381, found 408.1388.

Benzyl 4-phenyl-4-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)butanoate **5ag**

Following procedure 1.5.5 with (*E*)-N-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)-1-phenylmethanimine (0.2 mmol, 49.8 mg) and benzyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 59 μ L). The crude product was purified using flash

column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 69 %. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.36-7.21 (m, 12H), 6.47 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 5.12 (s, 2H), 4.68 (s, 1H), 4.40 (t, J = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 2.55-2.38 (m, 2H), 2.30-2.03 (m, 2H) ppm. $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (376 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -61.11 ppm. $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.4, 149.6, 142.2, 135.7, 128.9, 128.6, 128.4, 128.4, 128.2, 127.6, 126.5, 126.5, 126.2, 112.5, 66.6, 57.6, 32.9, 31.2 ppm.

1-Methylcyclopentyl 4-phenyl-4-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)butanoate **5ah**

Following procedure 1.5.5 with (*E*)-*N*-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)-1-phenylmethanimine (0.2 mmol, 49.8 mg) and 1-methylcyclopentyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 62 μ L). The crude product

was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 67 %. **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.36-7.26 (m, 6H), 7.24-7.22 (m, 1H), 6.50 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 4.84 (s, 1H), 4.39 (dd, J = 7.8, 5.9 Hz, 1H), 2.40-2.27 (m, 2H), 2.09 (pd, J = 14.2, 7.1 Hz, 4H), 1.76-1.59 (m, 6H), 1.55 (s, 3H) ppm. **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (376 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -61.09 ppm. **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.2, 149.7, 142.5, 128.9, 127.4, 126.5, 126.4, 126.3, 119.0-118.7 (d, CF_3), 112.4, 90.4, 57.9, 39.2, 39.2, 33.0, 32.3, 24.4, 23.8 ppm.

Methyl 2-(bis(*t*-butoxycarbonyl)amino)-4-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)-4-phenylbutanoate **5ai**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and methyl 2-(bis(*t*-butoxycarbonyl)amino)but-3-enoate (0.4 mmol, 120 mg). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography

in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 29 %. **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.39 (d, J = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 7.30 (t, J = 7.5 Hz, 2H), 7.24-7.17 (m, 1H), 6.67 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.47 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 5.05-4.96 (m, 1H), 4.50 (dd, J = 8.9, 4.6 Hz, 1H), 3.72 (s, 3H), 3.68 (s, 3H), 2.86-2.73 (m, 1H), 2.05 (ddd, J = 14.5, 9.0, 5.4 Hz, 1H), 1.47 (s, 18H) ppm. **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.2, 152.2, 151.9, 143.7, 141.7, 128.7, 127.1, 126.4, 114.8, 114.6, 83.4, 56.8, 56.0, 55.8, 52.3, 40.6, 28.0 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, m/z) [M+H⁺] calcd. for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{38}\text{N}_2\text{O}_7$ 515.2752, found 515.2751.

Following procedure 1.6.2 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and 2-(bis(*t*-butoxycarbonyl)amino)but-3-enoate (0.4 mmol, 120 mg). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography

in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 22 %. **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.33-7.28 (m, 4H), 7.21-7.16 (m, 1H), 6.68-6.62 (m, 2H), 6.47 (d, J = 6.1 Hz, 2H), 5.16 (dd, J = 7.7, 5.4 Hz, 1H), 4.38 (dd, J = 10.3, 3.9 Hz, 1H), 3.73 (s, 3H), 3.67 (s, 3H), 2.60

(ddd, $J = 15.4, 10.3, 5.3$ Hz, 1H), 2.28 (ddd, $J = 14.9, 7.8, 4.0$ Hz, 1H), 1.42 (s, 18H) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.8, 152.0, 151.9, 143.7, 141.3, 128.7, 127.1, 126.2, 114.8, 114.8, 83.3, 56.5, 56.2, 55.8, 52.4, 39.9, 27.9 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺, m/z) [M+H⁺] calcd. for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{38}\text{N}_2\text{O}_7$ 515.2752, found 515.2751.

Adamantan-1-yl 4-phenyl-4-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)butanoate **5aj**

Following procedure 1.5.5 with (*E*)-*N*-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)-1-phenylmethanimine (0.2 mmol, 49.8 mg) and adamantan-1-yl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 76 μL). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system.

For isolation, **4b** (0.3 mmol, 94.0 mg) was used as the photoreductant. **Yield:** 70 %. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.31 (h, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 6H), 7.23 (dd, $J = 5.7, 2.8$ Hz, 1H), 6.50 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 2H), 4.84 (s, 1H), 4.39 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 1H), 2.49-2.20 (m, 2H), 2.17 (s, 3H), 2.11-2.00 (m, 8H), 1.67 (s, 6H) ppm. ^{19}F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -61.1 ppm. ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 172.8, 149.8, 142.6, 128.8, 127.4, 126.5, 126.4, 126.2, 118.9-118.6 (d, CF_3), 112.4, 81.1, 57.9, 41.4, 36.2, 33.0, 32.6, 30.9 ppm.

2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethyl 4-phenyl-4-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)butanoate **5ak**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-(trifluoromethyl)aniline (0.2 mmol, 25 μL), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μL), and 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethyl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 74 μL). The

crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 34 %. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.37-7.26 (m, 7H), 6.52 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 2H), 4.75 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H), 4.42 (dd, $J = 13.0, 6.0$ Hz, 1H), 4.30-4.19 (m, 2H), 3.71-3.67 (m, 2H), 3.65-3.60 (m, 2H), 3.58-3.54 (m, 2H), 3.50 (q, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 2H), 2.53-2.38 (m, 2H), 2.26-2.04 (m, 2H), 1.19 (t, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 3H) ppm. ^{19}F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -61.1 ppm. ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.5, 149.7, 142.3, 128.9, 127.5, 126.5, 126.5, 126.3, 119.0-118.8 (d, CF_3), 112.5, 70.7, 69.8, 69.1, 66.7, 63.9, 57.7, 33.0, 31.2, 15.1 ppm. HRMS (ESI⁺, m/z) [M+H⁺] calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{28}\text{NO}_4\text{F}_3$ 440.2043, found 440.2033.

4'-(di-*p*-tolylamino)-[1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl 4-phenyl-4-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)butanoate **5al**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-(trifluoromethyl)aniline (0.2 mmol, 25 μ L), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and 4'-(di-*p*-tolylamino)-[1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl acrylate (0.4 mmol, 167.8 mg). The crude product was

purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 43 %. **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.53 (d, J = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 7.38 (d, J = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 7.35 (d, J = 3.9 Hz, 3H), 7.31 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.05 (ddd, J = 21.3, 10.6, 6.3 Hz, 14H), 6.55 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 4.69 (s, 1H), 4.52 (t, J = 6.6 Hz, 1H), 2.69 (td, J = 6.9, 2.7 Hz, 2H), 2.31 (s, 6H), 2.30 – 2.17 (m, 2H) ppm. **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (376 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -61.1 ppm. **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 172.3, 149.6, 149.4, 147.8, 145.2, 142.1, 138.8, 133.1, 132.7, 130.0, 129.9, 129.0, 127.7, 127.6, 126.6, 126.5, 126.3, 124.8, 124.6, 122.5, 121.6, 112.6, 57.6, 35.5, 32.8, 31.3, 20.8 ppm.

13-Methyl-17-oxo-7,8,9,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-decahydro-6H-cyclopenta[*a*] phenantren-2-yl 4-phenyl-4-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)butanoate **5am**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-(trifluoromethyl)aniline (0.2 mmol, 25 μ L), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and estrone acrylate (**0.24** mmol, 77.9 mg). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 50 %.

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.36 (t, J = 5.0 Hz, 2H), 7.33-7.22 (m, 5H), 6.81 (dd, J = 8.5, 2.4 Hz, 1H), 6.74 (d, J = 1.8 Hz, 1H), 6.54 (d, J = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 4.70 (d, J = 5.4 Hz, 1H), 4.51 (dd, J = 12.8, 6.1 Hz, 1H), 3.02-2.79 (m, 2H), 2.66 (tt, J = 11.1, 5.7 Hz, 2H), 2.51 (dd, J = 18.8, 8.6 Hz, 1H), 2.44-2.35 (m, 1H), 2.34-1.97 (m, 7H), 1.69-1.41 (m, 7H), 0.91 (s, 3H) ppm. **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (376 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -61.08 ppm. **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 172.5, 149.6, 148.4, 142.1, 138.2, 137.6, 129.2, 129.0, 127.7, 126.6, 126.5, 126.5, 126.3, 125.7, 121.5, 121.2, 119.3, 118.9, 118.6, 112.6, 57.6, 50.5, 47.9, 44.2, 38.0, 35.9, 32.8, 31.6, 31.3, 29.4, 26.3, 25.8, 21.6, 13.8 ppm.

2,5,7,8-Tetramethyl-2-(4,8,12-trimethyltridecyl)chroman-6-yl 4-phenyl-4-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)butanoate **5an**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-(trifluoromethyl)aniline (0.2 mmol, 25 μ L), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and α -

tocopherol acrylate (**0.24** mmol, 116.4 mg). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 37 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.37-7.33 (m, 4H), 7.29 (dd, J = 10.0, 6.4 Hz, 3H), 6.54 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 4.82 (d, J = 6.1 Hz, 1H), 4.54 (dd, J = 13.0, 6.3 Hz, 1H), 2.81-2.65 (m, 2H), 2.58 (t, J = 6.7 Hz, 2H), 2.38-2.18 (m, 2H), 2.09 (s, 3H), 1.97 (s, 3H), 1.93 (s, 3H), 1.78 (ddq, J = 19.8, 13.2, 6.7 Hz, 2H), 1.59-1.46 (m, 2H), 1.38 (d, J = 4.8 Hz, 3H), 1.26 (t, J = 8.7 Hz, 12H), 1.18-1.06 (m, 7H), 0.89-0.84 (m, 12H) ppm. **¹⁹F NMR** (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -61.12 ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 172.6, 149.6, 142.2, 140.4, 129.0, 127.6, 126.5, 126.5, 126.3, 124.8, 123.2, 117.5, 112.6, 75.2, 57.7, 39.4, 37.4, 37.3, 32.8, 30.8, 29.7, 28.0, 24.8, 24.5, 22.7, 22.6, 21.1, 20.6, 19.8, 19.7, 13.0, 12.2, 11.9 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, m/z) [$M+H^+$] calcd. for C₄₆H₆₄N₁O₃F₃ 736.4911, found 736.4942.

(2S,3R,4R,5S,6S)-2-(Acetoxymethyl)-6-(2-((4-phenyl-4-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)butanoyl)oxy)ethoxy)tetrahydro-2H-pyran-3,4,5-triyl triacetate **5ao**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-(trifluoromethyl)aniline (0.2 mmol, 25 μ L), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μ L), and β -D-galactose

pentaacetate acrylate (**0.24** mmol, 107.1 mg). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 80 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.37-7.29 (m, 6H), 7.24 (d, J = 2.9 Hz, 1H), 6.53 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 5.40-5.33 (m, 1H), 5.19 (dd, J = 13.2, 5.1 Hz, 1H), 5.01 (ddd, J = 10.5, 3.4, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 4.78 (s, 1H), 4.49 (dd, J = 7.9, 3.2 Hz, 1H), 4.42 (t, J = 6.6 Hz, 1H), 4.28-4.20 (m, 2H), 4.18-4.07 (m, 2H), 4.02-3.96 (m, 1H), 3.91-3.84 (m, 1H), 3.79-3.69 (m, 1H), 2.43 (t, J = 7.0 Hz, 2H), 2.25-2.09 (m, 5H), 2.04 (s, 3H), 2.01-1.94 (m, 6H) ppm. **¹⁹F NMR** (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -61.1 ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.3, 173.2, 170.4, 170.2, 170.1, 169.4, 149.7, 142.2, 142.2, 128.9, 127.6, 126.5, 126.5, 126.3, 112.5, 101.3, 70.8, 68.7, 67.3, 67.0, 63.5, 61.2, 57.6, 57.5, 32.9, 31.1, 31.1, 20.7, 20.7,

20.6, 20.6 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, *m/z*) [M+H⁺] calcd. for C₃₃H₃₈NO₁₂F₃ 698.2419, found 698.2387.

2-(*t*-Butyl)-6-(3-(*t*-butyl)-2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzyl)-4-methylphenyl 4-phenyl-4-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)butanoate **5ap**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-(trifluoromethyl)aniline (0.2 mmol, 25 μL), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μL), and Irganox @3052 acrylate (**0.24** mmol, 94.7 mg). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 58 %. **¹H NMR** (400

MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.31 (t, *J* = 6.2 Hz, 4H), 7.27-7.24 (m, 1H), 7.20 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.08 (s, 1H), 7.04 (s, 1H), 6.74 (d, *J* = 1.2 Hz, 1H), 6.66 (s, 1H), 6.49 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 5.11 (s, 1H), 4.74 (d, *J* = 25.3 Hz, 1H), 4.55 (s, 1H), 3.56 (d, *J* = 14.2 Hz, 2H), 2.78 (s, 2H), 2.27 (m, 5H), 2.20 (s, 3H), 1.38 (s, 9H), 1.30 (s, 9H) ppm. **¹⁹F NMR** (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -61.1 ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.6, 151.0, 149.5, 145.2, 142.0, 141.1, 136.7, 135.9, 131.6, 130.0, 129.0, 128.6, 127.9, 127.6, 127.1, 126.6, 126.5, 126.4, 126.4, 126.3, 126.2, 124.4, 123.6, 119.2, 118.9, 112.6, 57.6, 35.5, 34.7, 34.6, 32.7, 32.4, 31.9, 30.6, 29.8, 29.0, 26.5, 26.4, 22.9, 22.7, 21.2, 20.8, 14.1 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, *m/z*) [M+H⁺] calcd. for C₄₀H₄₆NO₃F₃ 646.3503, found 646.3517.

(10*S*,13*R*,16*S*)-10,13-dimethyl-3-oxohexadecahydro-1*H*-cyclopenta[*a*]phenanthren-16-yl 4-phenyl-4-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)butanoate **5aq**

Following procedure 1.6.2 with 4-(trifluoromethyl)aniline (0.2 mmol, 25 μL), benzaldehyde (0.2 mmol, 20 μL), and stanolone

acrylate (**0.24** mmol, 82.7 mg). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 47 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.41-7.29 (m, 7H), 6.53 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 4.78 (d, *J* = 5.4 Hz, 1H), 4.65 (dd, *J* = 12.2, 4.7 Hz, 1H), 4.44 (dd, *J* = 12.8, 6.2 Hz, 1H), 2.49-1.98 (m, 10H), 1.78-1.64 (m, 4H), 1.51-1.31 (m, 7H), 1.24-1.14 (m, 3H), 1.03 (s, 3H), 0.97-0.85 (m, 3H), 0.77 (d, *J* = 13.0 Hz, 2H) ppm. **¹⁹F NMR** (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -61.1 ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 211.8, 173.7, 158.8, 149.7, 142.4, 128.9, 127.5, 126.5, 126.3, 119.0-118.8 (d, CF₃), 112.5, 83.2, 57.8, 57.7, 53.8, 50.6, 46.7, 44.7, 42.8, 38.5, 38.1, 36.9, 35.7, 35.2, 33.0, 31.4, 31.2, 28.8, 27.6, 23.5, 20.9, 12.2, 11.5 ppm.

Methyl 2-((2S)-1-(phenylamino)-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-2-yl)acetate **7a**

Following procedure 1.5.3 with aniline (0.2 mmol, 18 μ L) and methyl (*E*)-4-(2-formylphenyl)but-2-enoate (0.2 mmol, 40.8 mg). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 61 %. **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.29 (d, J = 7.4 Hz, 1H), 7.19 (ddd, J = 12.1, 11.6, 4.2 Hz, 5H), 6.74 (t, J = 7.8 Hz, 3H), 4.74 (d, J = 7.3 Hz, 1H), 3.91 (s, 1H), 3.66 (s, 3H), 3.22 (dd, J = 18.9, 10.7 Hz, 1H), 2.79 (dd, J = 14.8, 4.8 Hz, 1H), 2.72-2.63 (m, 2H), 2.56 (dd, J = 14.8, 7.9 Hz, 1H) ppm. **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.2, 148.0, 144.4, 141.5, 129.4, 127.9, 126.8, 124.9, 124.2, 117.6, 113.0, 63.4, 51.6, 45.2, 37.7, 36.3 ppm.

Methyl 2-((2S)-1-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-2-yl)acetate **7b**

Following procedure 1.5.3 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg) and methyl (*E*)-4-(2-formylphenyl)but-2-enoate (0.2 mmol, 40.8 mg). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 67 %. **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.27 (s, 1H), 7.21 (d, J = 4.0 Hz, 2H), 7.15 (td, J = 8.0, 4.1 Hz, 1H), 6.79 (d, J = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 6.68 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.63 (d, J = 7.2 Hz, 1H), 3.76 (s, 3H), 3.64 (s, 3H), 3.20 (dd, J = 18.8, 10.6 Hz, 1H), 2.76 (dd, J = 14.8, 4.7 Hz, 1H), 2.68-2.60 (m, 2H), 2.52 (dd, J = 14.8, 7.9 Hz, 1H) ppm. **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.2, 152.3, 144.7, 142.2, 141.5, 127.8, 126.8, 124.8, 124.2, 115.1, 114.5, 64.4, 55.8, 51.6, 45.0, 37.8, 36.2 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, m/z) [$\text{M}+\text{H}^+$] calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{NO}_3$ 312.1594, found 312.1580.

Methyl 2-((2S)-1-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-2-yl)acetate **7c**

Following procedure 1.5.3 with 4-(trifluoromethyl)aniline (0.2 mmol, 25 μ L) and methyl (*E*)-4-(2-formylphenyl)but-2-enoate (0.2 mmol, 40.8 mg). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 51 %. **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.44 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.28 (d, J = 1.2 Hz, 2H), 7.23-7.16 (m, 1H), 6.75 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 4.80 (d, J = 6.2 Hz, 1H), 4.30 (s, 1H), 3.66 (s, 3H), 3.25 (q, J = 10.3 Hz, 1H), 2.79-2.66 (m, 3H), 2.65-2.56 (m, 1H) ppm. **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$**

(376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -61.1 ppm. ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.0, 150.5, 143.4, 141.4, 128.2, 127.0, 126.9, 126.8, 126.8, 126.8, 126.3, 125.0, 124.0, 123.6, 119.3, 119.0, 112.1, 63.0, 51.7, 45.0, 37.6, 36.2 ppm.

t-Butyl 2-((2*S*)-1-(phenylamino)-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-inden-2-yl)acetate **7d**

Following procedure 1.5.3 with aniline (0.2 mmol, 18 μ L) and *t*-butyl (*E*)-4-(2-formylphenyl)but-2-enoate (0.2 mmol, 49.3 mg). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 55 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.29 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 1H), 7.25-7.12 (m, 5H), 6.79-6.68 (m, 3H), 4.73 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 3.96 (s, 1H), 3.21 (dd, *J* = 14.5, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 2.78-2.57 (m, 3H), 2.52-2.39 (m, 1H), 1.46 (s, 9H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 172.0, 148.1, 144.6, 141.7, 129.4, 127.8, 126.7, 124.8, 124.1, 117.5, 113.0, 80.6, 63.4, 45.4, 39.2, 36.1, 28.1 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, *m/z*) [M+H⁺] calcd. for C₂₁H₂₅NO₂ 324.1958, found 324.1967.

t-Butyl 2-((2*S*)-1-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-inden-2-yl)acetate **7e**

Following procedure 1.5.3 with *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg) and *t*-butyl (*E*)-4-(2-formylphenyl)but-2-enoate (0.2 mmol, 49.3 mg). The crude product was purified using flash column chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 46 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.29 (s, 1H), 7.22 (d, *J* = 4.1 Hz, 2H), 7.18-7.11 (m, 1H), 6.81 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 6.70 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 4.63 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 3.77 (s, 3H), 3.20 (dd, *J* = 14.6, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 2.66 (ddt, *J* = 16.0, 13.6, 6.5 Hz, 3H), 2.44 (dd, *J* = 14.8, 8.4 Hz, 1H), 1.45 (s, 9H) ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 172.1, 152.2, 144.9, 142.4, 141.7, 127.7, 126.7, 124.8, 124.1, 115.1, 114.5, 80.5, 64.5, 55.8, 45.3, 39.3, 36.1, 28.1 ppm. **HRMS** (ESI⁺, *m/z*) [M+H⁺] calcd. for C₂₂H₂₇NO₃ 354.2064, found 354.2080.

t-Butyl 2-((2*S*)-1-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-inden-2-yl)acetate **7f**

Following procedure 1.5.3 with 4-(trifluoromethyl)aniline (0.2 mmol, 25 μ L) and *t*-butyl (*E*)-4-(2-formylphenyl)but-2-enoate (0.2 mmol, 49.3 mg). The crude product was purified using flash column

chromatography in a EtOAc/heptane eluent system. **Yield:** 61 %. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.42 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.27-7.20 (m, 3H), 7.22-7.09 (m, 1H), 6.74 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 4.77 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 4.32 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 1H), 3.30-3.08 (m, 1H), 2.81-2.57 (m, 3H), 2.55-2.40 (m, 1H), 1.44 (s, 9H) ppm. **¹⁹F NMR** (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -61.0 ppm. **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 171.8, 150.6, 143.7, 141.6, 128.1, 126.9, 126.9, 126.8, 126.8, 126.7, 126.3, 125.0, 124.0, 123.6, 119.2, 118.9, 112.1, 80.8, 63.1, 45.1, 39.1, 36.1, 28.1 ppm.

(E)-*N*-(4-(Trifluoromethyl)phenyl)-1-phenylmethanimine

Following procedure 1.5.6 with 4-(trifluoromethyl)aniline (2.0 mmol, 0.25 mL) and benzaldehyde (2.0 mmol, 0.20 mL).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.42 (s, 1H), 7.93-7.87 (m, 2H), 7.64 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 7.55-7.40 (m, 3H), 7.25 (t, *J* = 4.0 Hz, 2H).

1.8 Reference

- [1] H. G. Roth , N. A. Romero , D. A. Nicewicz, *Synlett* **2016**, 27, 714–723.
- [2] J. A. Leitch, T. Rossolini, T. Rogova, J. A. P. Maitland, D. J. Dixon, *ACS Catal.* **2020**, 10, 2009–2025
- [3] M. J. Vainio, M. S. Johnson, *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **2007**, 47, 2462–2474.
- [4] D. Loco, N. Gelfand, S. Jurinovich, S. Protti, A. Mezzetti, B. Mennucci, *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2018**, 122, 1, 390–397.
- [5] Q. Q. Zhou, W. Guo, W. Ding, X. Wu, X. Chen, L. Q. Lu, W. J. Xiao, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2015**, 54, 11196–11199.
- [6] K. Kohara, A. Trowbridge, M. A. Smith, M. J. Gaunt, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2021**, 143, 19268–19274.
- [7] M. D. Heredia, W. D. Guerra, S. M. Barolo, S. J. Fornasier, R. A. Rossi, M. E. Budén, *J. Org. Chem.* **2020**, 85, 13481–13494.
- [8] D. Sheppard, R. Terrell, G. Henkelman, *J. Chem. Phys.* **2008**, 128, 134106.
- [9] P. Giannozzi, S. Baroni, N. Bonini, M. Calandra, R. Car, C. Cavazzoni, D. Ceresoli, G. Chiarotti, M. Cococcioni, I. Dabo, et al. *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **2009**, 21, 395502.
- [10] M. Das, M. D. Vu, Q. Zhang, X.-W. Liu, *Chem. Sci.*, **2019**, 10, 1687–1691.
- [11] E. Tatunashvili, B. Chan, P. E. Nashara, C. S. P. McErlean, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2020,18, 1812–1819.
- [12] J. A. Leitch, T. Rossolini, T. Rogova, D. J. Dixon, *ACS Catal.* **2020**, 10, 11430–11437.

1.9 Spectra

